

Cobalt ferrite (CoFe₂O₄) nanoparticles for evaluation of antibacterial activity

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Abstract : Spinel ferrite nanoparticles have been investigated in recent years, because of its high chemical stability, saturation magnetization and coercivity. Magnetic nanoparticles of cobalt ferrites were synthesized by combustion method. Iron nitrate (Fe(NO₃)₃·9H₂O) and cobalt nitrate (Co(NO₃)₂·6H₂O) were used as an oxidizers and glycine (C₂H₅NO₂) was used as a fuel for this method. By changing the oxidant to fuel ratio, the adiabatic temperature of the flame and the final product could be controlled. The properties of as prepared CoFe₂O₄ powder were thoroughly studied to understand the structural and magnetic behavior (using powder X-ray diffraction, field-emission scanning electron microscope with electron probe micro analysis and vibrating sample magnetometer). Cobalt ferrite magnetic nanoparticles are being used for the biomedical applications. The nanoparticles were found to possess antibacterial activity against *E. coli* and it showed the inhibition at a minimum concentration of 50 mg/L.

Keywords : CoFe₂O₄, PXRD, FE-SEM with EPMA and VSM.

Introduction

Ferrites have various applications in medical diagnostics¹, microelectromechanical system (MEMS) and data storage^{2,3}. The cobalt ferrite is one of the excellent material for high density magneto optical recording applications due to its admirable coercivity and saturation magnetization⁴. The cobalt ferrite belongs to cubic spinel structure. It is familiar and fundamental of iron oxide materials. The oxygen (O²⁻) ions from closed packing of FCC, cobalt (Co²⁺) ions, ferrous (Fe³⁺) ions are occupied tetrahedral (A) and octahedral (B) sites⁵. CoFe₂O₄ magnetic nanoparticles were synthesized in various methods to obtain their desirable size, shape and magnetic properties have been reported by researchers in recent years. Different methods adopted for preparing the CoFe₂O₄ nanoparticles are hydrolysis⁶, co-precipitation⁷, polyol⁸ and combustion method^{9,10}. Solution combustion method was simple, highly pure and uniform distribution with low cost preparation. The magnetic iron-based inorganic nanoparticle was used in biological and medical purposes. They are having small size with higher surface area to volume ratio provide higher sensitivity, better targeting and improved colloidal stability of the nanostructures.

These applications depend upon their properties of ferrite nanoparticles that are influenced by their composition and size¹¹. In this study, CoFe₂O₄ nanoparticles were synthesized by combustion method for the enhancement of magnetic property and investigations were also taken up to check the antibacterial activity to identify the biomedical application of the particle through well diffusion method and also to determine the minimum inhibitory concentration.

Experimental

CoFe₂O₄ magnetic nanoparticles were prepared by solution combustion method. Analytical grade of cobalt nitrate and iron nitrate were used as an oxidants. Glycine was taken as a fuel to control the reaction of combustion. The metal nitrates and fuel were dissolved in double distilled water to get the precursor solution. The preparation of precursor solution was taken with three different ratios. The solution was kept in the preheated furnace. Ignition was initiated for fuel decomposition point and it was allowed to catch the fire at the flash point. At the end of the combustion process, the fluffy foam of our final product was obtained without further calcinations steps.

Antibacterial assay :

Antibacterial activity for the cobalt ferrite nanoparticles were tested on Gram-negative bacteria *E. coli* by Well diffusion method with 6 different concentrations (50, 100, 200, 300, 400 and 500 mg/L) which was dispersed in the dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) solvent for the easy diffusion into the Agar. Each well was loaded with 0.1 ml of the sample solution. The plates were incubated overnight at 37 °C and zone of clearance was observed.

Results and discussion

The structural properties of CoFe_2O_4 nanoparticles were studied by Bruker D8 Advance (Germany) powder X-ray diffractometer (PXRD). Average crystallite size (D) was calculated from all peak values by Scherrer formula,

$$D = \frac{k\lambda}{\beta \cos \theta} \tag{1}$$

Here k is shape factor, λ is wavelength of the radiation, β is Full Width at Half Maximum (FWHM) of the diffracted pattern and θ is corresponding diffraction angle. By adjusting the oxidant to fuel ratio, we can control the adiabatic temperature and thereby control the crystallite size of the resultants¹⁰. The corresponding X-ray diffraction peaks are matching well with JCPDS data (card number # 00-022-1086) was shown in the Fig. 1 and hence it is proved that the CoFe_2O_4 was obtained in single phase without any impurities. The two strong bands corresponding to metal oxide stretching and vibration were confirmed by the Fourier transform infrared (FT-IR) analysis and they are identified at $419 \pm 5 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $575 \pm 5 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. These two bands are attributed to intrinsic lattice vibrations of octahedral and tetrahedral sites of the given spinel structure¹². The morphology of the cobalt ferrite has been studied by field emission scanning electron microscopy (FE-SEM) and it is shown in Fig. 2. The as prepared compounds are having high porous in nature. The voids and porous nature imputed the large amount of gases were released during the combustion reaction¹³. The elemental studies were carried out by electron probe micro analysis (EPMA) and it is shown in Fig. 2. It con-

Fig. 1. X-Ray diffraction pattern matched with JCPDS data.

Fig. 2. FE-SEM with EPMA result for as prepared CoFe_2O_4 .

firms that the composition consist of 13.55 : 26.29 : 60.16 mol % of cobalt, iron and oxygen respectively. Magnetic measurements were done by vibrating sample magnetometer (VSM) with the external field of 15000 Oe at room temperature. The as prepared cobalt ferrite magnetic nanoparticles were exhibits ferromagnetic behavior in room temperature measurement, it is shown in Fig. 3. Using the B-H curve, saturation magnetization (M_s) of 47.04 emu/g, remanence magnetization (M_r) of 14.44 emu/g and coercivity (H_c) of 947.43 Oe were calculated for the as prepared sample. The cobalt ferrite nanoparticles pos-

sess to have the effect on the pathogen *E. coli*. Fig. 3 indicates the zone of inhibition of about 3 mm at the minimum concentration of 50 mg/L.

Fig. 3. VSM and antibacterial activity on as prepared CoFe₂O₄.

Conclusion

The single phase of cobalt ferrite was confirmed by powder X-ray diffraction method and the crystallite size 16 ± 5 nm was calculated by Scherrer equation. The electron probe micro analysis confirms the compositions. The B-H curve shows that saturation magnetization (M_s) of 47 emu/g for the as prepared sample at room temperature. The antibacterial activity of the cobalt ferrite magnetic nanoparticles through well diffusion method was investigated and determined the minimum inhibitory concentration at 50 mg/L with 3 mm inhibition zone width.

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